

RRI report:

First version

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This project has used a standard methodology already defined by partner CIRCE and developed in several projects such as TIGON (GA 957769), WILSON (GA: 101147267), eFORT (GA: 101075665) and ALCHEMY (GA 101177996), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the conditions of the Grant Agreement for ESTELAR project (GA: 101192574).

AI contribution disclosure

During the preparation of this work, the author (s) used Chat GPT (OpenAI, version 5.1, accessed December 2025) with next main purposes. I) suggest wording, ii) refine grammar, iii) standardise inputs, iv) summarize content. After using this tool, the author (s) reviewed and edited the content and take full responsibility for its accuracy and integrity.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
COMTRADE	Common format for Transient Data Exchange
CRoF	Control Room of the Future
DSoF	Digital substation of the future
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GOOSE	Generic Object-Oriented Substation Event (protocol)
KOM	Kick Off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PAC	Protection, Automation and Control
PC	Project Coordinator
PMP	Project Management Plan
RTDS	Real-Time Digital Simulator
RTO	Research and Technology Organizations
SC	Steering Committee
SV	Sampled Values Protocol
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSO	Transmission System Operator
vPAC	Virtualized Protection, Automation and Control (PAC)
VS	Virtual substation
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document is deliverable “D1.4 – RRI report.- First version” of project ESTELAR (project reference: 101192574).

This deliverable aims to present the first approach towards Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) within ESTELAR project. Given ESTELAR’s nature as a digital, cyber-physical project on critical power infrastructure, the consortium has decided to adopt the full 6-axis RRI framework (Ethics, Gender Equality, Governance, Open Access, Public Engagement, Scientific Education) rather than a reduced subset. Ethics and Governance are particularly relevant because ESTELAR develops virtualised substation concepts, advanced communication architectures and data-intensive solutions that directly affect grid reliability, cybersecurity, responsibility allocation and regulatory compliance. A comprehensive RRI approach therefore ensures that ESTELAR’s technical outcomes are not only innovative and efficient, but also secure, transparent, accountable and aligned with EU values and stakeholder expectations across the entire electricity system.

The document is based on RRI methodology used and reported in projects CIRCE coordinated listed above. In this document the project and its objectives are summarizing at the same time as providing context for an overview of RRI and its’ application to the project.

The key activities and outcomes at month 12 are presented with the avenues for updates identified as technical reporting and future project deliverables.

1 Introduction and RRI Scope

ESTELAR aims to develop and validate next-generation digital substation technologies enabling advanced virtualisation, interoperability, and secure communication architectures for modern power systems. Through the integration of virtualised protection and automation functions, IEC-compliant data exchange, edge computing, and cross-vendor interoperability, ESTELAR contributes directly to the digital transformation, resilience, and flexibility of European electricity networks. The project brings together research organisations, industrial partners, SMEs and an associated DSO, ensuring complementary expertise across hardware, software, communication systems, cybersecurity, standardisation and field operation.

The application of RRI in ESTELAR supports both the technical objectives of the project and the broader ambition of enabling secure, interoperable and socially beneficial digital substations. This report summarises the approach, initial activities, and future actions to embed RRI principles throughout the project lifecycle, ensuring that ESTELAR's outcomes remain robust, inclusive, and aligned with EU policies on digitalisation, sustainability and societal well-being.

2 RRI basis in ESTELAR

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) provides a structured approach to align these technological developments with societal needs, safety requirements, ethical considerations, and long-term public value. As ESTELAR operates in the domain of critical energy infrastructure, the consortium adopts the full 6-axis RRI framework covering Ethics, Gender Equality, Governance, Open Access, Public Engagement and Scientific Education. This extended scope reflects the project's interaction with cybersecurity, data protection, operational continuity and stakeholder trust—dimensions where responsible innovation is essential to ensure security, transparency and compliance with European values and regulatory expectations.

Following the GREAT project (Governance of Responsible Innovation GA 321480) statement: *“Responsible research and innovation (RRI) is a way of thinking and doing that guides research and development in ethically appropriate ways. It*

ensures that social as well as commercial benefits are harnessed; and that any harm to the social and physical environment is obviated or minimised”¹

As can be seen in Figure 1 RRI is about working with all actors, from policy makers to business, industry or civil society organisations, on 6 thematic elements (called “axes”) and in the framework of 4 process dimensions.

Figure 1: RRI framework: 5 actors (green), 6 axes (yellow) and 4 process dimensions (blue)²

On the one hand, these 4 dimensions have been pointed to as central to and able to help anchor the broader concept of RRI. These dimensions underpin necessary actions that enable the operationalisation of RRI in practice:

1. Diverse and Inclusive: enabling the hearing of ‘new voices’ that may challenge what can be narrow ‘we know what’s good for you’ top-down approaches.
2. Open and transparent: boosting shared learning
3. Anticipative and Reflective: taking a forward view that takes account of opportunities, risks, environmental concerns, etc. as well as putting research

¹ [Governance of REsponsible innovATIOn | GREAT | Projekt | Results | FP7 | CORDIS | European Commission](#)

² Figure adapted from RRI Tools Project [Image source](#)

into context through the regular posing of questions regarding norms and values.

4. **Responsive and Adaptive:** making changes as experience is gained and knowledge is built, including taking action to address any unintended consequences.

On the other hand, these 6 axes link with European goals as focused on “justice and fundamental rights based on mutual trust”. They also fit with the direction of the EC where the desired “new industrial revolution” is required to be ethically founded with green energy, clean transport and smart communications systems taking their place in helping deliver sustainable growth, create high-value jobs and solve societal challenges.

1. **Ethics** aimed at increasing societal relevance and acceptability of research and innovation outcomes.
2. **Gender Equality** which highlights the need to integrate the gender dimension in the research and innovation context.
3. **Governance** aimed at focusing on the importance of all actors to share responsibility for science.
4. **Open Access** as a mean to boost innovation and increase the use of scientific results.
5. **Public Engagement** of all societal actors and their joint participation in the RRI process.
6. **Science Education** as a means to make change happen through raising awareness and embedding RRI into educational curricula.

3 RRI indicators in ESTELAR

3.1 Events and actions up to M12

This section presents actions addressed in the project during the first year of the project classified in the 6 axes above mentioned.

3.1.1 Ethics

During the first year, ESTELAR partners initiated actions to ensure ethical and secure implementation of research activities consistent with Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement:

- **Data protection requirements identified** in a dedicated workshop before submission of the Data Management Plan.

- **Security and confidentiality procedures established**, as required for work on critical energy infrastructure, including controlled access to testbed environments and documentation. Project SharePoint gathers only information for the consortium members, but does not gather any Personal Data, which is only stored at each partners servers to avoid sharing them with undesired stakeholders.
- **Risk identification during the GA meeting** focusing not only on project implementation, but also on technical challenges such as hardware and software complementarities, cybersecurity, unintended automation behaviour and safe operation of digital protection schemes.

These actions lay the foundation for ethical compliance throughout the technical phases commencing after M12.

3.1.2 Gender Equality

Consortium members fulfilled the Grant Agreement requirement of having institutional Gender Equality Plans where applicable, so the Grant Agreement Preparation was successfully addressing this point. Specifically, the list of partners and their status regarding GEP is presented below

- *CIRCE*. Available online. <https://www.fcirce.es/transparencia>
- *TUD*: Available online. <https://www.tudelft.nl/en/about-tu-delft/strategy/diversity-inclusion/policies/gender-equality-plan>
- *SIEMENS*: Available online. <https://www.siemens.com/es/es/empresa/temas-clave/diversidad.html>
- *CUERVA* has a GEP but it is not public online.
- *SOC-E* : is about to reach the number of 50 employees so they are considering to adopt a GEP in the upcoming years.
- *3SI*: is currently considering to adopt a GEP, although this is not binding for private entities with their characteristics. The potential impact of a GEP is specifically under evaluation.
- *R2M Solution*: internal draft version prepared aligned with the head of the Human Resources department. It is only available internally.
- *STEDIN*: available online <https://www.stedin.net/-/media/project/groep/files/persberichten/annual-report-2017-stedin-group.pdf?rev=b3eb9fbcd08647f28cd45a285e571e2d&hash=3D306FD6DF841B772B22D85B0BID0A99>

ESTELAR partners are committed to foster gender equality following the commitment in Horizon Europe programme. This commitment aims to have more women participating in research and innovation programmes and to have a better integration of gender dimension in the research and innovation projects.

In the framework of this project, gender perspective will be studied through its lifetime from two different perspectives:

1. When possible, developed solutions must aim to consider the gender dimension and to avoid any potential discrimination.
2. When possible, ESTELAR project partners will work towards gender balanced teams.

Thus, the KPIs for Gender Equality axis in ESTELAR project will be:

1. Percentage of women over the total workforce of the project.
2. Number of entities having a Gender Equity Plan implemented or foreseen. In this sense, it is worth mentioning that, at project’s Grant Agreement/annex 1/part B/section 1.2.7, it is mentioned that “A Project’s Gender Equality Plan (PGEP) will be developed starting from the very beginning of the project. The PGEP will define the pathway and requirements to ensure that gender dimension is fully considered and integrated within ESTELAR activities”. In this same direction, it is also worthy to mention that not all organizations are obliged to have a GEP in place.

Firstly, for a proper Gender Balance assessment, Figure 2 collects the relevant data according to participants’ roles and career stage to provide a first view at M12.

Figure 2: Gender balance per Role (a) and per Career Stage³ (b) at M12

Based on these figures, 4 main key conclusions could be drawn:

Leadership and seniority show male dominance: Men hold **83.3% of leadership roles**, with women at **16.7%**, showing a clear gender imbalance in decision-making positions.

Women concentrated in early and mid-career stages: Women are the majority in **C1 (55.6%)** and **D (66.7%)**, but men dominate **A (100%)** and **B (71.4%)**, so female presence declines with seniority

The pipeline is gendered but promising: There is strong female participation at entry and mid levels (D, D2, C1), but their low representation in senior categories and leadership suggests a risk of losing female talent before it reaches top positions.

Mismatch between category and leadership opportunities: Although women are numerous in C1 and D, this is not reflected in leadership roles, while men in comparable or slightly higher categories (e.g. B) are more likely to lead. This points to potential bias in role assignment and promotion.

Then, considering Gender balance per partner, not fairly well balanced, with women representing less than 20% of the workforce.

Table 1 shows that it is not fairly well balanced, with women representing less than 20% of the workforce.

Table 1 Gender balance at M12 (detail)

Beneficiary	Men	Women	% Women
1-CIRCE	5	2	28,6%
2-TUD	5	0	0,0%
3-SIEMENS	4	0	0,0%
4-CUERVA	4	1	20,0%
5-3SI	3	0	0,0%
6-SOC-E	4	1	20,0%
7- R2M-ES	2	1	33,3%
7.1-R2M-IT	1	2	66,7%
8-STEDIN	2	0	0,0%
	30	7	37

³ Being, Category A - Top Grade Researcher (Full professor/Director of research), Category B - Senior Researcher (Senior Researcher/Associate professor), Category C1 - Recognised Researcher (Researcher/Assistant professor), Category D - First stage researcher, Category D2 - Other First stage researcher

% Total	81,08%	18,92%	100%
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Early actions addressed so far include:

- Collection of gender-disaggregated data from partners through the Contact list and Funding & Tenders Portal to establish M12 baseline metrics.
- Gender balance monitoring in project governance bodies (GA, Steering Committee, Technical Committee), showing initial representation rates.
- Awareness measures promoted internally, including reminders to ensure balanced representation in meetings and dissemination materials.
- Inclusion of gender-sensitive language and representation in project communication outputs (web content, presentations, visual material).
- Grant visibility to women participating in the project in Social media posts

These actions prepare the consortium for more structured follow-up in later reporting periods.

Additionally, some other social media promotion on Women's day were carried out for the consortium promoting the Women's day and Engineering women day.

- <https://www.cuervaenergia.com/es/comunidad/la-energia-mas-humana/compromiso-dia-mujer/>
- <https://www.cuervaenergia.com/es/comunidad/la-energia-mas-humana/historias-inspiradoras-dia-de-la-m...>
- <https://www.cuervaenergia.com/es/comunidad/la-energia-mas-humana/dia-de-la-mujer-ingeniera/>
- <https://www.instagram.com/p/DLPho6ICH-1/>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:7345739277781143553/>
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/siemens_mint-elternabend-girlsday-ugcPost-7189249368850370561-WHYC/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_ios

Partner SIEMENS made the reflection of the internal percentage of women in management roles reaching the 22%, which is not reflecting the current scenario of the ESTELAR project.

3.1.3 Governance

Given the technological and operational implications of ESTELAR innovations, governance actions have focused on structured decision-making, transparency and coordination:

- Operationalisation of the ESTELAR governance structure (as defined in the Consortium Agreement), including regular Steering Committee, General Assembly meeting and Technical Committee meetings developed within each individual WP.
- Definition of decision-making process in the Consortium Agreement to set the basis of a fair and clear governance body internally in the consortium.
- Initial alignment with relevant standardisation bodies (IEC, ISO, VPAC ALLIANCE, CIGRE GROUP, IEEE), through expert analysis of partners, to ensure traceability between project outputs and regulatory frameworks. Partners SIEMENS and STEDIN have individual participants in the mentioned bodies
- Documentation of internal procedures for version control, data handling, publication approval and access rights management.

These governance mechanisms support the responsible development of technologies with direct impact on power system operations.

3.1.4 Open Access

As further detailed in the project Data Management Plan (DMP) (Sensitive) activities follow the “*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*” principle. Due to concerns varying from legitimate secrecy for commercial exploitation, or simply lack of public interest, not all activities in the project are open. However, according to the DMP, FAIR principles⁴ are applied to ensure that the maximum amount of results and data can be made open access.

As a practical application of these principles open scientific and other publications and data will be linked to via the website <https://www.estelar-project.eu/> with homepage shown in Figure 3, where new sections will be created in the upcoming months to upload the open access material generated.

⁴The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship- <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618> How to cite this article: Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* 3:160018 doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18 (2016).

Figure 3: ESTELAR website.

A ZENODO community for the project was also created (<https://zenodo.org/communities/estelar>) to be updated including Communication material, among other publicly available content as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: ESTELAR community in ZENODO

Moreover, different information from the project is shared via newsletters, videos, leaflets, and by means of partners participation at events.

Also, during the first 12 months, 2 open scientific publications have been prepared.

Table 2 ESTELAR Publications up to M12

Publication Title	Who?	Where?	When?
Simplemux traffic optimizer	CIRCE	Published	16/12/2025
Design and compatibility of different Stand Alone Merging Unit (SAMU) calibration testbeds	CIRCE	Published in Zenodo	8/09/2025
Calibration Compatibility Index for a Single SAMU Across Different Testbeds	CIRCE	Submitted to a journal	25/11/2025
Evaluation of a Low-Latency, High-Accuracy Intrusion Prevention System for Digital Substations	TUD	Submitted to a conference. IEEE PESGM	3/12/2025

Source code developed in the frame of ESTELAR is also being subject of open publication. In particular part of the work devoted for the first publication declared in Table 2, a software tool named “Simplemux” was released in GitHub. under GNU GENERAL PUBLIC LICENSE Version 3.

Table 3 ESTELAR Open software up to M12

Publication Title	Who?	Where?	When?
Simplemux	CIRCE	Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/17209552 Gitlab: https://gitlab.com/josemariasaldana/simplemux/	6/09/2025

Finally, it is also of relevance to mention the effort to identify potential datasets to be made openly accessible later, respecting security constraints typical of digital substation research. This was part of the workshop to prepare the DMP submission.

3.1.5 Public Engagement

With regards to Public Engagement axis, ESTELAR is working on different scenarios, and its status is being closely monitored in coordination with activities performed in the framework of tasks T6.1 “Communication and dissemination strategy” and T6.3 “Networking and synergies with former and on-going projects and initiatives”.

Up to M12, main actions carried out to engage as many people as possible to disseminate about ESTELAR project have been identifying and contacting sister projects and, to a lesser extent due to project stage, participating in events.

Referring sister projects, 8 projects have been identified, 3 contacted and, after initial meeting with project coordinators and communication and dissemination leaders, 2 of them were initially presented in our website to build up synergies. Table 4 presents sister projects identified in ESTELAR up to M12:

Table 4 Sister projects identified in ESTELAR up to M12

Acronym and Name	Coordinator	CORDIS link
Effort - Establishment of a FramewORk for Transforming current EPES into a more resilient, reliable and secure system all over its value chain	CIRCE	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101075665
SSTAR- Innovative HV Solid-State TrAnformer for maximizing Renewable energy penetration in energy distribution and transmission systems	CIRCE	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069702
TwinEU - Digital Twin for Europe	FRAUNHOFER	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101136119
INSIEME	UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES UPPER AUSTRIA	https://insieme.energy/index.html

Acronym and Name	Coordinator	CORDIS link
Interscada - Interoperable, Scalable and seCure Ac-Dc modular Automation system	FRAUNHOFER	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101173007
Data Cellar - Data hub for the Creation of Energy communities at Local Level and to Advance Research on them	RINA-C	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069694
Eddie - European Distributed Data Infrastructure for Energy	FH OO FORSCHUNGS & ENTWICKLUNGS GMBH	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069510
SYNERGIES- Shaping consumer-inclusive data pathwayS towards the eNERGy transition, through a reference Energy data Space implementation	TXT	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069839

Concerning events participation, there wasn't a major advance due to the preliminary stage of the project. Additional details will be found in D6.2 "Dissemination and Communication report. First version" planned to be submitted in M12. December 2025, with follow up and updated version in a yearly basis in D6.7 (M24-December 2026) and D6.8 (M36-December 2027)

Closely related to the activities referring project participation in events, it is worth noting that, during this first 12 months, 6 platforms and/or associations were mapped as interesting candidates to be in contact with and, as described above, actions with some of them have already taken place.

Table 5 Associations and Platforms identified on behalf of ESTELAR up to M12

Name	Status
ENTSO-E	Identified in GA
EDSO for smart grids	Identified in GA
EURELECTRIC	Identified in GA
The Council of European Energy Regulators	Identified in GA
EASE	Identified in GA
ENTSO-E Technopedia	Identified in GA

Topics ESTELAR is dealing with along the project execution which are subject to be included in the discussion of Associations and Platforms are:

- *System and communications architecture for virtual operation*
- *Virtualization of protections*
- *Virtualization of substations (VPAC)*
- *Power Quality*
- *Energy data*
- *Synchronization of devices.*
- *Cybersecurity*
- Grid protection
- Grid Digital twins
- Dataspaces
- Data acquisition, orchestration and synchronization

3.1.6 Science Education

Science education aims to contribute to innovative problem-solving and critical thinking in the society, to enhance citizens to participate in the research and innovation processes. This education will ensure interdisciplinary approaches in the future and a bigger stakeholders' involvement that makes the society more resilient and innovative.

As ESTELAR involves universities, research organisations and industrial partners, early educational actions already addressed include:

- Involvement of early-stage researchers and PhD candidates in requirements analysis, architecture design and technical meetings.
- Integration of ESTELAR topics into academic courses and seminars, particularly on digital substations, IEC standards and cybersecurity. Partner TUD is an University and topics related to ESTELAR are already part of the academia courses such as Cybersecurity of power grids (Master course). There is also an existing plan to include content generated in ESTELAR once it's ready.
- Integration of ESTELAR topics into the ongoing PhD research of a female researcher at CIRCE, who is developing her doctoral thesis directly aligned with the project's activities.
- Internal knowledge-sharing sessions among partners to harmonise understanding of virtualisation concepts, edge computing and digital protection principles.

- Identification of combined scientific publications from researcher and industrial partners (CIRCE+SOC-E).

These activities reinforce ESTELAR's educational impact from the beginning of the project.

Although the consortium is composed of only eight partners, the presence of one university (TUD) and one Research and Technology Organisation (CIRCE) provides a strong backbone for the Science Education axis. Their combined academic, training and knowledge-transfer capacities ensure that ESTELAR can meaningfully contribute to education-oriented activities, including the involvement of early-stage researchers together with senior experts, integration of project topics into academic curricula and specialised training on digital substation technologies. This makes Science Education being connected with industry sector thanks to the participation of DSO profiles such as CUERVA and STEDIN, as well as industrial partners such as SIEMENS, SOC-E and 3SI. This strategic axis will be covered throughout the project's duration thanks to the great skills complementarity of the consortia.

3.2 Events and actions planned until M36

Building upon the foundations set during the first 12 months of the project, ESTELAR will continue to strengthen its Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach across all six axes defined in section 2 until Month 36. Planned actions combine lessons learned from the first year, the project's technical roadmap, and best practices drawn from previous CIRCE-coordinated projects such as WILSON and ALCHEMY. Future activities aim to ensure that the development of virtualised substation technologies remains ethical, inclusive, transparent and aligned with stakeholder needs.

Next sections gather action points agreed at a consortium level to continue working on the 6 main axes.

3.2.1 Ethics

- Internal ethical review of communication and data exchange workflows, ensuring any processing of system operational data complies with GDPR and national regulations.

- Maintain continuous compliance with GDPR and security requirements, updating the ethical assessment as new datasets and test environments appear in WP2–WP5.
- Conduct ethical risk reviews during each major architecture or testbed update, focusing on data integrity, automation behaviour and cybersecurity.
- Develop guidelines to ensure ethical handling of system logs, communication traces and pseudo-operational data generated in laboratory environments.
- Introduce short ethics-awareness briefings for technical partners before major integration/testing cycles.

3.2.2 Gender Equality

- Regular monitoring of gender distribution across roles and career stages (M18, M36, M48), assessing progress against M12 baseline.
- Encourage balanced representation of women in technical committees, workshops and leadership roles where possible.
- Promote visibility of female experts through communications materials, presentations and dissemination events.
- Check internally those partners not having the GEP in place to assess the possibility to create one. For example:
 - *CUERVA has a GEP but it is not public online. In 2026 the document will be made available in their website*
 - *SOC-E : is about to reach the number of 50 employees so they are considering to adopt a GEP in the upcoming years.*
 - *3Si: is currently considering to adopt a GEP, although this is not binding for private entities with the characteristics. The potential impact of a GEP is specifically under evaluation.*
 - *R2M Solution: even if the GEP is not legally obligated to have the GEP, and the plan is not currently active, the company has a draft version prepared and has been working on it (together with the head of the Human Resources department, and available internally). R2M have everything prepared for when the workforce exceeds 50 employees, at which point they would have three months to submit the plan to*

the competent authorities after forming the negotiating commission. Despite the GEP is not active, there are existing protocols in place for labor reception and integration and for workplace harassment which considers GE aspects.

- Implement targeted actions for categories where women are underrepresented . Several parter such as CUERVA and SIEMENS promoted in Social media the women participation in Women’s day, Engineering woman day
 - <https://www.cuervaenergia.com/es/comunidad/la-energia-mas-humana/compromiso-dia-mujer/>
 - <https://www.cuervaenergia.com/es/comunidad/la-energia-mas-humana/historias-inspiradoras-dia-de-la-m...>
 - <https://www.cuervaenergia.com/es/comunidad/la-energia-mas-humana/dia-de-la-mujer-ingeniera/>
 - <https://www.instagram.com/p/DLPho6lCH-1/>
 - <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:7345739277781143553/>
 - https://www.linkedin.com/posts/siemens_mint-elternabend-girlsday-ugcPost-7189249368850370561-WHYC/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_ios

3.2.3 Governance

- Maintain transparent decision-making processes in the General Assembly, Steering Committee and Technical Committee through structured agendas and documented votes.
- Ensure that RRI topics, including ethics, gender, and data protection, become fixed agenda points at least once per year in the General Assembly meetings.
- Strengthen engagement with standardisation bodies, Industry associations and platforms through participation in working groups relevant to digital substation virtualisation.
- Update internal procedures (data handling, publication approval, version control) as ESTELAR progresses to integration and demonstration phases.

3.2.4 Open Access

- Continuously update the ESTELAR ZENODO community with public deliverables, open datasets (when applicable) and dissemination materials.
- Publish scientific papers in relevant journals and conferences on virtualisation, IEC 61850 architectures, edge computing and secure substation automation.
- Make available non-sensitive testbed datasets aligned with FAIR principles, focusing on synthetic traffic traces and virtualised function outputs.
- Maintain an up-to-date website with accessible results and communication materials.
- Develop a set of “educational technical notes” that explain key ESTELAR concepts (e.g., virtualised protection, CDCs, merging units) for external audiences. R2M will coordinate internally in the consortium to develop this activity within WP6 to target relevant academic audiences.

3.2.5 Public Engagement

- Participate in sectoral events such as ENLIT, CIGRE IEEE Conferences and other events already gathered in the calendar presented under D6.2 to be submitted in December 2026 to disseminate project achievements.
- Maintain and expand the mapping of sister projects to enable coordinated actions or joint sessions, especially with projects where topics identified by the consortium matches such as digital substations, cybersecurity and grid automation.
- Organise ESTELAR-driven workshops during M24–M48, aligned with WP6 dissemination plans, targeting DSOs, TSOs, manufacturers and regulators.
- Promote communication actions via websites and social media channels of partners.

- Organise and participate in public webinars showcasing project outcomes and technical demonstrations. This activity is framed under Task 6.6 and C&D commitments
- Participating in webinars to increase synergies

3.2.6 Science Education

- Continue the involvement of PhD students and early-stage researchers from TUD and CIRCE in development, integration and analysis tasks in WP2–WP5.
- Integrate ESTELAR concepts into lectures, master’s theses and technical seminars at TUD.
- Develop training materials explaining virtualised substation concepts and their implications for the future workforce.
- Support publication of scientific articles and conference contributions by academic and RTO partners.
- Training sessions using ESTELAR testbeds for industry. This activity will be linked to C&D actions.
- material for YouTube channel to be created by partners with the support and coordination of WP6L

4 Conclusions

This first RRI report (D1.4), delivered at Month 12 of ESTELAR, provides an initial picture of how Responsible Research and Innovation principles are being integrated into a project focused on digital, cyber-physical and critical power infrastructure. The adoption of the full 6-axis framework (Ethics, Gender Equality, Governance, Open Access, Public Engagement and Science Education) has proved appropriate for the nature and ambition of ESTELAR.

During the first year, concrete steps have been taken in all axes: ethical and security requirements have been identified and embedded in procedures; a first gender baseline and initial measures to promote balance and visibility have been established; governance structures defined in the GA and CA are operational; open access has started through the website, ZENODO community and first publications; public engagement has begun via sister-project mapping and initial event participation; and science education is already visible through the involvement of PhD and early-stage researchers and integration of ESTELAR topics in academic and training activities.

Looking ahead to Month 36, the planned actions will build on this foundation: strengthening monitoring and mitigation in Ethics and Gender Equality, deepening the use of governance structures to support responsible decision-making, expanding open access outputs, intensifying stakeholder engagement, and further leveraging the academic and industrial profile of the consortium for education and skills development. Updates to RRI activities and indicators will be reflected in D1.6 “RRI report – M24” (M24–December 2026) as well as in technical reports and relevant WP6 deliverables over the remainder of the project.

5 References

<https://www.rri-leaders.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/0-Keynote-presentation-Papanagnou.pdf>

<https://www.great-project.eu/Deliverables10>

<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/97891>

EU [Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025](#): This is the EU’s flagship document outlining strategic actions to advance gender equality across various sectors, including research and innovation

[European Institute for Gender Equality \(EIGE\)](#): EIGE provides research, data, and tools to support gender equality policies in Europe, including resources for integrating gender in research and innovation.